

**CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY TEACHERS IN
THE DELIVERY OF CURRICULUM AND
INSTRUCTION THROUGH MODULAR DISTANCE
LEARNING**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

2022

Volume: 5

Issue: 1

Pages: 356-366

Document ID: 2022PEMJ326

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7294487

Manuscript Accepted: 2022-05-11

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in the Delivery of Curriculum and Instruction Through Modular Distance Learning

Carlos Tian Chow C. Correos*, Nico Michael D. Huelma

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aims to determine the problems faced by teachers in the conduct of curriculum and instructions in distance learning. The study employed a descriptive-correlational design. The study used a descriptive method in describing the characteristics of the demographics and the delivery of curriculum and instructions. Three thousand eighty-seven respondents were drawn from the population. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that it is very challenging for the respondents in the delivery of curriculum and instructions as to quality content, assessment, and support for distance learning. The findings revealed that age, position, and the number of years in teaching have a strong association with the delivery of curriculum and instruction. The number of training was inadequate; there should be relevant training appropriate to the modality implemented. The findings of the study provide data to the Division of Surigao del Sur to know the different factors affecting the delivery of the curriculum and instruction in modular distance learning. The results also serve as a springboard to revisit the assessment practices and methodologies used by the teachers in the delivery of assessment in the new normal as well as the capacity building for school leaders focused on the curriculum and instructions for future improvements on the implementation of modular distance learning in the new normal.

Keywords: *Curriculum and Instruction, Assessment, Content, Modular Distance Learning*

Introduction

While the coronavirus infected over 700,000 people in the Philippines, a total of over 24 million Filipino students in both public and private schools were affected by the changes in education. Face-to-face learning modality has been suspended and this paved the way for the implementation of Modular Distance Learning as an urgent response in ensuring continuity of education delivery. The education department is in the process of adapting to the new normal form of education at present, and continuous innovations of teachers and school leaders including the active involvement of other stakeholders are the driving force for its success.

The impact of school closures where children were stuck at home with limited or no access to learning platforms posed major adjustments that challenged the management and delivery of the curriculum. According to Kofahi and Srinivas (2004), three major practical issues influenced distance learning delivery. This includes the separation of teacher and learner for most of each instructional process, the use of educational media to unite teacher and learner in carrying out course contents, and the provision of two-way communication between teacher, tutor, or educational agency and the learner.

To mitigate the possible problems in the continuous

education delivery for the school year 2020-2021, the Department of Education released DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020 containing the Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. The BE-LCP provided clear guidance to all offices, units, schools, and community learning centers (CLCs), to the learners and their parents, partners, and stakeholders. This also included a package of education interventions that will respond to basic education challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Since DepEd schools are not ready for Online Distance Learning (ODL), and TV/Radio-Based Instructional Delivery (RBI/TVBI), the department implemented Modular Distance Learning through print. This modality allowed the schools to continue education and attain its mission and vision which is to provide quality and accessible education to every Filipino learner (Quinones, 2020). The use of printed modular delivery required teachers to design learning activity materials that will be distributed to learners instead of textbooks and other school learning resources that are still inadequate.

Through printed modality, the teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners. The use of multiple platforms via e-mail, telephone, text message/instant messaging among others is encouraged to learners for asking assistance

from the teacher. Whenever possible, teachers shall do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance or learners in marginalized situations including those in hard-to-reach areas (Llego, 2020).

Additionally, education is no longer held within the school and parents serve as facilitators and partners of teachers in the learning delivery. The new modality requires parents to play a vital role as home facilitators and their primary role in modular learning is to establish a connection and guide the child toward learning the lessons (FlipScience, 2020). The homes become “class homes” for learners since the teaching and learning process happens at home.

As the school year progressed from its opening last October 5, 2020, more difficulties were encountered in the day-to-day delivery of basic education services. These difficulties include Communication, the ways of providing direct teaching, asking and answering questions: discussing the lesson, and communicating instructions about activities and other matters about the course; the Materials, the way content lessons are based on, references, and materials needed for learning activities; the Learning Activities and Assignments, the activities that would facilitate learning that could include role-playing, case studies, group discussions and presentations, and problem-solving; and Assessments, the means of measuring the progress of the students’ learning (NUADU Education, 2020).

Moreover, schools in Surigao del Sur Division faced issues including how students cope with long periods of not being with classmates for physical and social interaction; how teachers manage the stresses of teaching and student learning from a distance; how school leaders and teachers manage the systems, processes, and operations in remote educational delivery; how parents manage the additional new responsibility of children “going to school at home”; and for external partners, how will they sustain their support to the resources of the school.

In recent survey results, most of the learners are having difficulty with the new learning modality. 90% of the learners in schools had a hard time answering their modules and half of them do not have enough time to accomplish all their modules within a week (Dangle and Sumaoang, 2020). Furthermore, most of the students cannot answer all their modules independently, which is why they badly need the assistance of others.

Several studies prompted challenges encountered by teachers in Modular Distance Learning. Some of these mentioned that most students cannot study

independently. 70% of them cannot easily follow instructions in the modules, thus, modules were often submitted late, and most of the answer sheets are empty. Teachers' lack of resources for the reproduction and delivery of modules has been delayed. There are instances when printers are not functioning well. In the worst case, electricity interruption caused the stoppage of operation. Therefore, teachers have trouble with printing and mass production of modules.

There are instances that some learners cannot finish their modules on time because they mostly spend their study time teaching their siblings with their modules and helping their parents in the field. Teachers also assume that students' answers in their modules have no validity, and most probably, mastery of the lessons is impossible to attain. Parents as well lack the knowledge to assist their child/children because some parents did not finish their studies and the contents of the lessons are beyond their comprehension. Some teachers also have weak cellphone signals. Lastly, teachers have a lot of paper works; papers to check and record.

Despite the challenges encountered, teaching, and learning in distance classes need new methods and practices. It requires our teachers and school leaders to adjust the pedagogical process. In the same way, keeping children engaged over long periods without physical activity to break up the learning day will be a major challenge, especially for younger children.

This research aimed to investigate the challenges encountered by teachers in the delivery of curriculum and instruction in the new normal. The results were used to strategically plan ways forward to ensure the engagement of learners' creative learning. Addressing challenges ensure that distance education will run without the presence of teachers and check on how well learners are doing at home. This research answered the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of Surigao del Sur teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Position;
 - 1.3. Number of years in teaching; and
 - 1.4. Number of Training attended?
2. What are the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery in terms of:
 - 2.1. Delivery of Quality Content;
 - 2.2. Delivery of Quality Assessment;
 - 2.3. Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers’

profiles and the challenges encountered in the delivery of curriculum and instruction in modular distance learning?

Literature Review

On Modular Distance Learning

The DepEd's Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for the School Year 2020-2021 in the Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency provided clear guidelines for the delivery of education during the pandemic times. The BE-LCP emphasized that education delivery must: (1) ensure protection of health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and personnel, and prevent the further transmission of COVID-19; (2) ensure learning continuity through K-12 curriculum adjustments, alignment of learning materials, deployment of multiple learning delivery modalities, provision of corresponding training for teachers and school leaders, and proper orientation of parents or guardians of learners; (3) facilitate the safe return of teaching and non-teaching personnel and learners to workplaces and schools/CLCs, taking into consideration the scenarios projected by the Department of Health (DOH) and the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases in the Philippines (IATF) complemented by other credible sources and balanced with DepEd's risk assessments; (4) be sensitive to equity considerations and concerns, and endeavor to address them the best education possible; and (5) link and bridge the BE-LCP to DepEd's pivot to quality and into the future of education, under the framework of Sulong EduKalidad and Futures Thinking in Education.

According to Bernardo (2020), modular learning is the most popular type of Distance Learning across countries. In the Philippines, since public schools are not equipped with technology to deliver synchronous and asynchronous blended modalities, learning through printed modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method for parents and children. This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where internet and cellphone signals are not accessible for online learning.

According to DepEd, Modular Distance Learning is an alternative learning modality for the new normal that features individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever applies to the learner. Learners under Modular Distance Learning

can use other resources such as Learner's Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials.

Usually, teachers will have to deliver appropriate learning materials. Students can also access these materials by downloading electronic copies through their computer, tablet PC, or smartphone as options.

The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners. If possible, they will conduct home visits to check on each student's progress and performance. Likewise, learners may ask for assistance from the teacher via email, telephone, text message/instant messaging, etc. Parents or any member of the family, on the other hand, may serve as a guide or para-teachers to learners at home.

It is in this context that parents/guardians play a vital role in the fruitful outcome of this endeavor. Their guidance and support inspire the kids to work hard and be motivated to study. Under the new normal, school personnel, parents, and stakeholders must work jointly with each other for the learners to acquire the best quality education that they deserve (Irasga 2021).

However, there are some limitations of modular distance delivery using self-paced learning. There is a lack of interaction between instructor and learners or among learners if a self-paced program is the sole method of instruction in a course. In this single-path learning, the lockstep method is followed, and learning can become monotonous and uninteresting. On the other hand, open-ended (discovery-type) projects may allow for too much divergence in what learners experience and accomplish.

Additionally, a lack of self-discipline combined with procrastination can result in delaying the completion of the required study for some learners. Many learners must develop new habits and patterns of behavior before they are successful in self-paced learning. Setting deadlines (weekly or monthly) within which learners can adjust to their own study pace is often required and beneficial for some learners.

This self-paced method often requires cooperation and detailed team planning among the faculty involved in the course. Also, coordination with other support services of the organization (e.g., facilities, media, reproduction) may become necessary or even critical. It must be considered that more preparation and expense are typically involved in developing self-paced units compared with lecture presentations.

On the Delivery of Quality Content

In the modular distance learning delivery, teachers must ensure that learning materials are consistent with their quality. Content knowledge must be prioritized since mastery of content requires a deep understanding of the lesson.

According to Morisson, et.al. (2019), a high-quality self-paced learning program includes the following specific features:

1. Learning activities must carefully be designed to address specific objectives where the self-paced unit is organized into comparatively small, discrete steps, each one treating a single concept or segment of content. The size of the steps can vary, but they must be carefully sequenced.
2. Activities and resources must be carefully selected in terms of the required instructional objectives.

Moreover, Craig and Cooper (2018), emphasized that the quality of learning materials must be:

1. Logical or sequential. The steps reflect occupational steps, prerequisite knowledge and abilities, and difficulty
2. Self-contained learners can pick up (or access) the module and begin work without instructor intervention and can proceed through the module based on clear instructions about what to do in all likely situations, including what to do at the end of the module.
3. Comprehensive—the module includes, or references, all the content that is relevant to the learning objectives or competencies.
4. Cohesive—the module content is well integrated and contributes to the learner’s mastery of the competencies within a reasonable time. Self-paced learning modules can be comprehensive including all the objective content, activities, and assessments needed for the learner to complete the module independently. This is often the case when a new teacher creates his/her own CBE curriculum. The teacher pulls all the content together in one place (or even writes the content from scratch). All the modules that the learner needs are in one place, whether online or on paper.

On the Delivery of Quality Assessment

Assessment plays an important role in the process of learning and motivation. The types of assessment tasks that we ask our students to do determine how they will approach the learning task and what study behaviors must be used. In the words, what and how students learn depends to a major extent on how they think they will be assessed.

According to the Global Education Monitoring Report

(2020), one of the issues in educational aspects is the assessment practices in modular distance learning. Previously, schools have adopted assessment practices such as using previous grades from exams, applying observational assessments of teachers, and considering prior grade expectations. These emerging assessment practices, however, have put education stakeholders under some challenges specifically in the assessment of learning outcomes.

As a response, DepEd issued DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020 the Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan to provide schools and teachers guidance on the assessment of student learning. This policy ensures that schools must adopt assessment and grading practices that can most meaningfully support student development and respond to varied contexts during the pandemic.

Assessment as an important instructional component must capsule information as regards knowledge, skills, and values that students have learned (Allen, 2004). This information can be obtained only from directly examining student work to assess the achievement of learning outcomes. However, considering the current global crisis restricting normal conditions of learning, assessment practices must be reconsidered from new and different perspectives (Cahapay, 2020).

Moreover, Morisson (2019) believed that self-paced learning and assessment must be given the most attention in instructional design. The principles of learning indicate that much evidence supports the belief that optimum learning takes place when a student works at his or her own pace and is actively involved in performing specific learning tasks, assessments, and experiences success in learning. Self-paced learning and the provision of quality assessment methods involve the following:

1. The learner’s mastery of each step must be checked before he or she proceeds to the next step. Therefore, it is necessary to require the learner to demonstrate mastery of the content through different assessment activities.
2. The learner then must receive immediate confirmation of mastery of the objectives based on assessment results. With each success and failure, the learner confidently advances to the next step.
3. When the learner has difficulty understanding the material or fails to master the objectives for a unit, further study may be necessary, or the learner may ask the teacher for help. Thus, the learner is continually

engaged in active learning and receives immediate feedback.

4. of the teacher involved in a self-paced learning program changes because less time is spent making presentations and more time is devoted to addressing learners in group sessions, consulting with learners, and managing the learning environment.

Distance learning programs presuppose an already developed degree of autonomy for self-learning and self-motivation among learners. Learning autonomy is important in distance learning, however, many learners, may not yet have developed sufficient autonomy for self-learning. The totality of distance learning programs lacks mechanisms for teachers to assess and provide feedback and formative guidance to students. Modular distance learning programs are uni-directional interfaces that do not offer opportunities for teachers to assess and correct students' learning pathways. When students lack regular feedback from teachers, they may fail to maintain their current learning levels and struggle to develop new knowledge and skills through self-learning, as required.

On the Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning

Despite the promises and advantages of distance learning, some problems need to be resolved. These problems in the delivery of quality support to distance learning. This influences the overall quality of distance learning as a product.

An increase in students' engagement is characterized by high-quality teaching and learning (Ashwin & McVitty, 2015). Instructional support from teachers is the most dominant factor determining student engagement and learning becomes more efficient and relevant to them if they develop new skills, knowledge, abilities, and attitudes using appropriate materials (Rivet & Krajcik, 2008).

The learning materials must contain summaries of material, and training, and covers how students build knowledge. Supplementary instructional material must be developed by teachers to provide ease, encourage, improve, and promote teaching and learning activities to improve and facilitate effective processes of instruction (Matarazzo, et. al, 2001). Learning materials must offer new approaches and learning opportunities that enhance students' knowledge and helps them overcome deficiencies (Gordon & Nicholas, 2013). Teachers also must be aware of the prerequisite topics so that intervention could be done to address students' least mastered competencies

(Herrera & Dio, 2016) so that they can provide supplemental materials appropriate to learners' needs.

According to School Education Getaway (2020), the biggest challenge related to supporting pupils was keeping all of them motivated and engaged (43%), involving pupils from socially disadvantaged homes (36%), involving disaffected pupils (19%), and supporting those with special needs or disabilities (18%).

Teachers need more time spent with individual learners specifically in diagnosing their difficulties, giving help, and monitoring their progress. They also need more opportunities to interact with learners on higher intellectual levels concerning their problems, interests, and uses of the subject content, and more time required for preparing, gathering, and organizing materials for use of learners.

Instance and Dumont (2010) believed that a personalized approach to learning is highly sensitive to individual needs and highly adapted to differences between learners. This means that teaching and learning in distance delivery is not a solitary endeavor but must be individualized based on individual preferences. It also means that both collaborative and autonomous learning opportunities responsive to the needs of each learner, under the guidance of learning goals defined by education systems. Intervention approaches of this nature include developing individualized development and learning plans, providing one-on-one or very small group coaching or tuition, and, for older students, providing flexible learning options, pathways, and transitions for older students.

Parent engagement, according to Ferlazzo (2011), is about engaging families to become partners with the school. Parent involvement includes creating better school–community relationships contributing to greater gains in academic achievement and enhancing emotional development.

Home-based activities that parent typically engage in are important in how parents view their role in supporting their children and supporting the school (Epstein, 1995). One barrier noted by parents/guardians is a lack of or poor timing of communication between the school and home. Some sentiments of parents about how time affects involvement were expressed in two ways: conflicts with other events, and conflicts with parents' work schedules.

Learners with special educational needs and those in

marginalized families and locations have the right to free support measures provided by the school and school facility. The support measures include the necessary modifications of educational and school services concerning the health condition, cultural environment, or other life conditions of the pupil. It is guaranteed that education and school services are provided in structurally and technically adjusted spaces.

Learners with special needs and in marginalized contexts encompass a broad range of students with varying cognitive, physical, emotional, and behavioral learning needs. These learners demonstrate diverse abilities and academic achievement. Early studies conducted in the United States (Alper & Ryndak, 1992) report that students with needs tend to underperform relative to peers without needs on assessments and that this achievement gap tends to widen over time as students progress.

Pedagogical intervention must support the education of a pupil with special education needs in subjects where it is necessary to strengthen his/her education, compensate for insufficient home preparation for teaching, and to develop the pupil's learning style. To effectively teach learners with special needs and marginalized learners, teachers must have effective pedagogical practices designed to accommodate a broad group of students' learning needs (Barnard-Brak & Lechtenberger, 2010). These pedagogies will allow learners in different circumstances to embrace learning within the context of their needs.

Methodology

A descriptive, survey research design was chosen to capture the challenges encountered by teachers in the delivery of curriculum and instruction in the new normal education.

Participants

The respondents were 3,087 out of 6,000 teachers of the Surigao del Sur Division. Convenience sampling was used since all teachers available to respond to the questionnaires were accommodated as respondents. An online link consisting of the different questions was sent to teachers and responses. Data gathered were analyzed with the establishment of a 5% margin of error. Instruments of the Study

Procedure

Data were collected from the survey questionnaire posted online exclusively for Surigao del Sur teachers. The questionnaire contained the profiling of teachers as well as a set of questions focused on the challenges encountered by teachers in the delivery of curriculum and instruction in the new normal.

A total of 15 questions focused on the delivery of quality content, delivery of quality assessment, and delivery of quality support to distance learning. Questions captured information on all variables including the test of hypothesis. Each statement was represented by descriptions and Likert equivalent.

The survey questionnaire was validated by experts to ensure that it measures what it intends to measure. It was tried out on 40 teachers, and it gained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 89% which means the questionnaire is reliable and can be used in the survey method.

The researchers floated the questionnaire through an online platform for one week to give time for teachers to respond completely to the survey. Since the way it was floated was online, results were readily tallied and recorded in the google system for interpretation and analysis.

The researchers utilized the mean and standard deviation for descriptive analysis of the data gathered and applied the Pearson Product Moment Correlation to make inferences on the correlation of the variables.

Ethical Considerations

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sought the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study with the teachers of the whole division. After the approval, a special meeting of all district supervisors was done to present the purpose of the study as well as the process and the ongoing activities that they are involved in research. This lets them understand the research agenda and the benefits that the study contributes to the whole division.

To ensure teachers' privacy of information is protected, the link for the questionnaire is set to DepEd users only. Teachers were also notified that the results of their responses are off the record and interpretation based on data gathered ensured the confidentiality of their identity.

Results and Discussion

The discussion is based on the data and information gathered through the questionnaire used in the conduct of the study.

Table 1. Profile of Surigao del Sur Teachers

Profile of Teachers	Frequency N=3087	Percent (%)
<i>Age</i>		
20 to 29 years old	787	25.5
30 to 39 years old	1045	33.9
40 to 49 years old	677	21.9
50 to 59 years old	505	16.4
60 years old and above	73	2.4
<i>Position</i>		
Teacher 1	1272	41.2
Teacher 2	641	20.8
Teacher 3	951	30.8
Master Teacher 1	172	5.6
Master Teacher 2	51	1.7
<i>Length of Service</i>		
1 to 5 years	1135	36.8
6 to 10 years	784	25.4
11 to 15 years	350	11.3
16 to 20 years	262	8.5
21 years and above	556	10
<i>Number of Trainings Attended</i>		
1 to 5 trainings attended	2738	88.7
6 to 10 trainings attended	292	9.5
11 to 15 trainings attended	57	1.8

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents which revealed that 33.9% or 1045 are 30 to 39 years old, 25.5% or 787 are 20 to 29 years old, 21.9%, or 677 are 40 to 49 years old, 16.4% or 505 are 50 to 59 years old, and 2.4% or 73 of the respondents are 60 years old and above.

The table also shows that most of the respondents are Teacher 1 which comprised 41.2% of the population or 1272 respondents, 30.8% or 951 of the respondents are Teacher 3, 20.8% or 641 are Teacher 2, 5.6% or 172 respondents are Master teacher 1, and only 1.7% or 51 respondents are Master Teacher 2.

Furthermore, the table reveals that 1135 or 36.8% of the respondents are teaching in the Department of Education for 1 to 5 years already, 25.4% or 784 respondents are in the service for 6 to 10 years, 11.3% or 350 respondents are teaching for 11 to 15 years already, 8.5% or 262 respondents are in the service for 16 to 20 years, and only 10% or 556 respondents have served for 21 years and above.

On the number of training attended regarding the distance learning modality, table 1 shows that most of

the teachers have attended 1 to 5 trainings only which comprised 88.7% or 2738 respondents. There 292 or 9.5% of the respondents have attended 6 to 10 trainings, and only 1.8% or 57 respondents have attended 11 to 15 trainings.

Evident in the table presented is the number of training attended by the teachers about modular distance learning. In this new normal in education teachers need to update and upgrade their pedagogical approaches to support learners especially those with special needs and learning gaps. Omar (2014) believed that training has for many years been the driving force behind many changes that have occurred in teaching and learning. Teachers, like any other profession, must stay current on the most recent thoughts, thinking, and research in their industry. As educators, professionals, and those responsible for the education of the future generation, this encourages lifelong learning.

Table 2. Challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery

Delivery of Quality Content	\bar{X}	s.d.	Qualitative Description
The development of learning materials where content knowledge of the subject is effectively communicated to learners	3.72	0.79	Very Challenging
The contextualization/customization of learning materials to address diversity	3.76	0.78	Very Challenging
The inclusion of engaging strategies and activities in the learning materials for enjoyable learning	3.71	0.78	Very Challenging
The development of easy and practical learning materials to address academic ease	3.68	0.8	Very Challenging
The development of multi-disciplinary learning materials to ensure learners' exploratory and collaborative skills	3.72	0.77	Very Challenging
Overall	3.72	0.78	Very Challenging

Table 2 shows the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery as to the Delivery of Quality Content. The overall mean of 3.72 with a qualitative description of Very Challenging reveals that the teachers have encountered difficulties in the delivery of quality content in the modular distance delivery. The teachers are very challenged in the contextualization/customization of learning materials to address diversity manifested by a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.78. On the development of learning materials where content knowledge of the subject is effectively communicated to learners, the teachers responded very challenging with a mean of 3.72 and a standard deviation of 0.79. The teachers were also very challenged in the development of multi-disciplinary learning materials to ensure learners' exploratory and collaborative skills

bearing a mean of 3.72 and a standard deviation of 0.77. On the inclusion of engaging strategies and activities in the learning materials for enjoyable learning, the respondents find it very challenging to have a mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.78. Lastly, the teachers responded very challenging on the development of easy and practical learning materials to address academic ease with a mean of 3.68 and a standard deviation of 0.80.

In the distance learning modality, the development of learning materials entails extra effort and in-depth knowledge among the teachers to address the different learning needs of the learners which makes it very challenging for the teachers. Developing a self-paced learning material requires cooperation and detailed team planning among the faculty involved in the course. It must be considered that more preparation and expense are typically involved in developing self-paced units compared with lecture presentations.

According to Morisson, et.al. (2019), a high-quality self-paced learning program includes learning activities that are carefully designed to address specific objectives where the self-paced unit is organized into comparatively small, discrete steps, each one treating a single concept or segment of content and that activities and resources must be carefully selected in terms of the required instructional objectives.

Table 3. *Challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery*

<i>Delivery of Quality Assessment</i>	<i>\bar{X}</i>	<i>s.d.</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
The provision of wide range of assessment tools to learners	3.7	0.78	Very Challenging
The development of flexible assessment tools to learners	3.7	0.8	Very Challenging
The delivery of authentic performance assessment to measure learner's understanding	3.79	0.81	Very Challenging
The validity and reliability of assessment results to determine learner's progress	3.76	0.82	Very Challenging
The utilization of assessment results to determine effectiveness of the instruction provided	3.71	0.79	Very Challenging
Overall	3.73	0.8	Very Challenging

Table 3 shows the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery as to the Delivery of Quality Assessment. The overall mean of 3.73 with a qualitative description of Very Challenging is a manifestation that the teachers have encountered challenges in the delivery of quality assessment in the modular distance delivery. Bearing the highest mean

of 3.79 and standard deviation of 0.81, the teachers responded very challenging in the delivery of authentic performance assessment to measure learners' understanding. On the validity and reliability of assessment results to determine learner's progress, the respondents find it very challenging manifesting a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.82. On the utilization of assessment results to determine the effectiveness of the instruction provided, the teachers responded very challenging supported by a mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.79. Additionally, the provision of a wide range of assessment tools to learners and the development of flexible assessment tools for learners have the same mean of 3.70 and standard deviation of 0.78 and 0.80 respectively.

According to the Global Education Monitoring Report (2020), one of the issues in educational aspects is the assessment practices in modular distance learning. These necessitate teachers to design assessments tailored fit to the needs and learning capacities of the students such as flexible and validated assessment tools to ensure the quality of assessment.

Moreover, Morisson (2019) believed that self-paced learning and assessment must be given the most attention in instructional design. Much evidence supports the concept that best learning occurs when a student works at his or her own pace and is actively involved in accomplishing specified learning activities, assessments, and experiences learning success, according to learning principles.

Table 4. *Challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery*

<i>Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning</i>	<i>\bar{X}</i>	<i>s.d.</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
The development of supplementary materials to cater different learning gaps	3.72	0.78	Very Challenging
The provision of intervention (remediation, reinforcement, enhancement) to address learner's learning gaps	3.76	0.79	Very Challenging
The communication to learners, parents and guardians to update learner's progress	3.71	0.86	Very Challenging
The establishment of connection to learners in improving autonomy, motivation, self-determination, self-regulation	3.73	0.79	Very Challenging
The provision of support to learners with special educational needs and learners in marginalized areas	3.74	0.83	Very Challenging
Overall	3.73	0.81	Very Challenging

Table 4 shows the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery as to the Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning. The overall mean of 3.73 with a qualitative description of Very Challenging reveals that the teachers have encountered challenges in the delivery of quality support to distance learning in the modular distance delivery. The teachers responded very challenging in the provision of intervention (remediation, reinforcement, enhancement) to address learners' learning gaps having a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.79. In addition, the provision of support to learners with special educational needs and learners in marginalized areas bears a mean of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.83 resulting in a very challenging qualitative description. On the establishment of a connection to learners in improving autonomy, motivation, self-determination, and self-regulation, the respondents find it very challenging manifested by a mean of 3.73 and a standard deviation of 0.79. The development of supplementary materials to cater to different learning gaps has a mean of 3.72 and standard deviation of 0.78 reveals that the respondents are very challenged. Lastly, the respondents find it very challenging to communicate with learners, parents, and guardians to update learners' progress revealing a mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.86.

Instructional support from teachers is the most dominant factor determining student engagement and learning becomes more efficient and relevant to them if they develop new skills, knowledge, abilities, and attitudes using appropriate materials (Rivet & Krajeck, 2008). This means that teachers must address very well the challenges encountered in the delivery of quality support to encourage positive development among learners.

Teachers must also intensify their linkage to the parents and guardians to help improve learners' performance and address the different learning gaps that take place at home. Parent engagement, according to Ferlazzo (2011), is about engaging families to become partners with the school. Parent involvement includes creating better school-community relationships contributing to greater gains in academic achievement and enhancing emotional development.

Table 5. *The relationship between teachers' profiles and the challenges encountered*

	Age	Position	Length of service	Number of Trainings Attended
A. Delivery of Quality Content	0.037	0.039	0.047	0.015
	0.041	0.03	0.01	0.409
	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Accept H ₀
B. Delivery of Quality Assessment	0.051	0.05	0.064	0.02
	0.005	0.005	0.001	0.255
	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Accept H ₀
C. Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning	0.057	0.057	0.061	0.003
	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.857
	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Accept H ₀

Table 5 shows that there is a significant relationship between the age and the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery in terms of Delivery of Quality Content, Delivery of Quality Assessment, and Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning. It also reveals that the Teaching Position has a significant relationship with the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery in terms of Delivery of Quality Content, Delivery of Quality Assessment, and Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning. Additionally, the table shows that there is a significant relationship between the length of service and challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery in terms of Delivery of Quality Content, Delivery of Quality Assessment, and Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning. Lastly, the table shows that there is no significant relationship between the number of training attended by the teachers relative to modular distance learning and the challenges encountered by teachers in the curriculum and instructional delivery in terms of Delivery of Quality Content, Delivery of Quality Assessment, and Delivery of Quality Support to Distance Learning.

The table further shows that the age, teaching position, and length of service have something to do with the ability of the teachers to face the different challenges in the teaching profession, especially in this time of pandemic where education has shifted to modular distance learning. It also reveals that the training attended by the teachers is not directly related to modular distance learning delivery which caused them to encounter different challenges in terms of quality content, quality assessment, and quality support to distance learning.

An increase in students' engagement is characterized by high-quality teaching and learning (Ashwin & McVitty, 2015). Instructional support from teachers is the most dominant factor determining student engagement and learning becomes more efficient and relevant to them if they develop new skills, knowledge, abilities, and attitudes using appropriate

materials (Rivet & Krajcik, 2008).

Learning materials must offer new approaches and learning opportunities that enhance students' knowledge and helps them overcome deficiencies (Gordon & Nicholas, 2013). Teachers also must be aware of the prerequisite topics so that intervention could be done to address students' least mastered competencies (Herrera & Dio, 2016) so that they can provide supplemental materials appropriate to learners' needs.

Training and development can be thought of as processes designed to enhance the professional knowledge, skills, and attitudes of educators so that they might, in turn, improve the learning of students. Training is an important part of teacher preparation programs, especially for those aspects of teaching that are more skill-like in their conception, but there are many other important aspects of teaching that can only be nurtured through reflective strategies and experiences. However, training must be appropriate and relevant to the needs of teachers in the delivery of instructions (Rahman et.al., 2011).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. (1) Teachers found it very challenging in the delivery of curriculum and instruction as to quality content, assessment, and support to distance learning. (2) Age, position, and the number of years in teaching have a significant relationship in the delivery of curriculum and instruction. However, there is no significant relationship between the number of training attended by teachers in the delivery of the new normal and the challenges encountered by teachers in teaching and learning delivery.

From the conclusions derived from this study, the following recommendations were given: (1) There is a need to revisit the assessment practices and methodologies used by teachers in the delivery of assessment in the new normal. (2) There shall be designing of assessment tools appropriate to the new learning modality. (3) There is a need to revisit the training provided for teachers if training were appropriate to the modality implemented. (4) There must be ongoing capacity building for school leaders focused on the delivery of quality content, assessment, and support for distance learning. (5) There is a need to provide consistent monitoring, evaluation and technical assistance to be provided to schools to

address the gaps and mitigate risks and challenges in the delivery of teaching and learning in the new normal.

References

- Allen, J. D. (2005). Grades as valid measures of academic achievement of classroom learning. *The Clearing House*, 78(5), 218-223.
- Alper, S., & Ryndak, D.L. (1992). Educating students with severe handicaps in regular classes. *The Elementary School Journal*, 92(3), 373-387.
- Ashwin, P., & McVitty, D. (2015). The meanings of student engagement: Implications for policies and practices. *The European Higher Education Area*. Cham: Springer.
- Barnard-Brak, L., & Lechtenberger, D. (2010). Student IEP participation and academic achievement across time. *Remedial and Special Education*, 31(5), 343-349.
- Bernardo, J. (2020, July 30). Modular Learning most preferred parents: DepEd. *ABSCBN News*.
- Cahapay, Michael B. Reshaping Assessment Practices in a Philippine Teacher Education Institution during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Crisis. *Pedagogical Research* 2020, 5(4), em0079 e-ISSN: 2468-4929.
- Craig, M.A. & Cooper, M.S. (2018) Curriculum and Instructional Materials Center: A Division of the Oklahoma Department of Career and Technology Education. Printed in the United States of America by the Oklahoma Department of Career and Technology Education. Stillwater, Oklahoma 74074-4364
- DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020. Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in the Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency.
- DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020 the Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan
- Epstein, J. (1995, May). School/family/community partnerships: Caring for the children we share. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 701-712.
- Ferlazzo, L. (2011). Involvement or Engagement? *Educational Leadership*, 68(8), 10-14
- FlipScience (2020, October 5). 'Tagapagdaloy': How Filipino parents can help ensure successful modular distance learning. FlipScience - Top Philippine Science News and Features for the Inquisitive Filipino. h
- Gordon, S., & Nicholas, J. (2013) Students' conceptions of mathematics bridging courses. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 37(1), 109-125.
- Herrera, C., & Dio, R. (2016). Extent of Readiness of Grade 10 Students for General Mathematics of Senior High School in Sorsogon City, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 3(4), 1-8.
- Istance, D. and H. Dumont (2010), "Future directions for learning environments in the 21st century", in *The Nature of Learning: Using Research to Inspire Practice*, OECD Publishing, Paris,

Matarazzo, K.L., Durik, A.M., & Delaney, M.L. (2010). The effect of humorous instructional materials on interest in a math task. *Motivation and Emotion*, 34, 293–305.

Morrisson, G.R., Ross, S.J., Morrisson, J.R., & Kalman H.K. (2019). *Designing Effective Instruction*, 8th edition. Copyright ©, 2019, Wiley. All rights reserved.

Kofahi, Najib A. and Srinivas, Nowduri (2004). Distance Learning: Major Issues and Challenges. *Instructional Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*.

Irasga, Patricia Mae A. (2021). The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Secondary Public Schools Of Region III. DepEd-Bataan.com

Llego, MA. (2020). DepEd Learning Delivery Modalities for School Year 2020-2021. TeacherPh.

NUADU Education, 2020. What You Need to Know About the DepEd Learning Continuity Plan.

Quinones, M. T. (2020, July 3). DepEd clarifies blended, distance learning modalities for SY 2020-2021. Philippine Information

Agency.

Rivet, A.E., & Krajcik, J. S. (2008). Contextualizing instruction: Leveraging students' prior knowledge and experiences to foster an understanding of middle school science. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 45(1), 79-100.

Survey on Online and Distance Learning Results. *School Education Getaway*. 2020. August 6, 2020. Erasmus.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Carlos Tian Chow C. Correos

Department of Education
Surigao Del Sur - Philippines

Nico Michael D. Huelma

Carrascal National High School
Surigao Del Sur - Philippines